

Book Review:

**Organizational management. Concepts and practices
[Managementul organizației. Concepte și practici] (Panaite Nica &
Andrei Ștefan Neșțian – Coord., Iași: Alexandru Ioan Cuza
University Publishing, 2024)**

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Recently, the second edition (revised and expanded) of the academic book *Managementul organizației. Concepte și practici* [Organizational Management. Concepts and Practices] was published. This work was developed by a team of faculty members from the Faculty of

Economics and Business Administration (Department of Management, Marketing, and Business Administration) at "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iași. The editorial endeavor, carried out with the support of the university's publishing house, provides an up-to-date synthesis of fundamental knowledge in the field. The coordinators of the book, Panaite Nica and Andrei Ștefan Neșțian, have structured the content and presentation in a way that makes it a valuable resource for economics students, managers of various economic entities, and anyone interested in the latest developments in organizational management [1]. The book's structure, which systematically and comprehensively covers key managerial concepts and practices, includes 10 chapters (Number of pages:

394, Format: 17 x 24 cm), each focusing on essential aspects of management: (1) Management Issues; (2) Organizational Culture; (3) Ethics and Corporate Social Responsibility; (4) Fundamentals of Planning; (5) Managerial Decision-Making; (6)

Organization and Organizational Structures; (7) Human Resource Management Activities; (8) Motivation in Organizations; (9) Leadership; and (10) Managerial Control. We believe that this contribution by the authors—Panaite Nica, Adriana Prodan, Aurelian Iftimescu, Andrei Neșțian, Irina Manolescu, Daniela Tatiana Corodeanu Agheorghiesei, Silviu Tiță, Cătălin Ioan Clipa, Viorica Maria Bedrule Grigoruță, Alexandra Luciana Guță, Carmen Claudia Aruștei, and Elena-Sabina Turnea—represents an excellent tool for students, researchers, and practitioners interested in the fundamentals and applications of organizational management. Here, we briefly outline some key elements that make up the book. Chapter 1 - *Management Issues* – Explores the definition of management, its efficiency and effectiveness, managerial functions, categories of managers, their competencies and roles, as well as how managerial skills are acquired. Chapter 2 - *Organizational Culture* – Analyzes the influence of national culture on organizational culture, the factors shaping organizational culture, and various theoretical evaluation models, including those developed by Hofstede, GLOBE, and DOCS. Chapter 3 - *Ethics and Corporate Social Responsibility* – Discusses the importance of business ethics, managerial responsibilities, the moral development of organizations, and the implementation of ethics and compliance programs. Chapter 4 - *Fundamental Elements of Planning* – Details strategic planning processes, the formulation of organizational mission and vision, management by objectives, and various types of organizational strategies. Chapter 5 - *Managerial Decision-Making* – Provides insights into the decision-making process, decision typologies, and decision-making methods, including multi-criteria models such as ELECTRE and AHP. Chapter 6 - *Organization and Organizational Structures* – Explains the division of labor, departmentalization, hierarchical levels, and models of organizational structures, both classical and modern. Chapter 7 - *Human Resource Management Activities* – Presents objectives and strategies for recruitment, selection, career development, performance management, and employee compensation. Chapter 8 - *Motivation in Organizations* – Addresses motivation theories, reward-based motivation strategies, and optimizing employee motivation in various contexts. Chapter 9 - *Leadership* – Analyzes different leadership styles, leader typologies, and the importance of involving subordinates in the decision-making process. Chapter 10 - *Managerial Control* – Examines managerial control processes and methods, including employee behavior control and the use of financial resources. Through its comprehensive approach and clear structure, this book provides both a solid theoretical foundation and practical examples useful for developing managerial skills. "Organizational Management. Concepts and Practices" proves to be an indispensable guide for those who wish to understand and apply modern management principles in their organizations.

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Brief Information about the team of management specialists (Co-authors of this Work):

Panaite Nica - is an Emeritus Professor and PhD supervisor in Management. He has published textbooks, monographs, studies, and articles in the fields of Organizational Management, Educational Management, and Human Resource Management. He has extensive experience in management consulting and research project leadership.

Adriana Prodan - is a Professor, PhD supervisor in Management, and former Director of the SDEAA Doctoral School. She coordinated the first professionalization program in Human Resource Management in Romania, developed in 2001 as a postgraduate program. She is the author of several articles and books on management.

Aurelian Iftimescu - is a retired Lecturer, with teaching and research interests in Management, Quantitative Decision Techniques, Management Information Systems, and Human Resource Management. He has published multiple textbooks, studies, and articles in these fields and has completed specializations in France, the Netherlands, and Ireland.

Andrei Ștefan Neșțian - is a Professor with a 24-year academic career in Management. For 16 years, he has been actively involved in managerial practice as a Management consultant and partner in a consultancy firm specializing in attracting non-reimbursable funds.

Irina Manolescu - is an Associate Professor, PhD in Economics, specializing in Management. Her research activity, supported by participation in over 30 projects, is reflected in the publication of more than 160 articles in specialized journals and volumes, as well as over 20 books and book chapters.

Daniela Tatiana Agheorghiesei (Corodeanu) - is a Professor, PhD supervisor in Management. She has extensive managerial experience, having served as the head of the UAIC Extension in Bălți, Republic of Moldova. She is a co-founder of the Institute of Corporate Governance and Sustainability at Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași.

Maria Viorica Bedrule-Grigoruță - is a Professor with a PhD in Economics, specializing in Management and PhD supervisor. She has been active in education for over 30 years, authoring/co-authoring 8 books, 80 articles, and participating in 8 research grants/projects. She has completed specializations in France, Germany, and the USA.

Silviu Tiță - is a Professor teaching courses on Management, Organizational Diagnosis, Organizational Performance Evaluation and Analysis, and Strategic Management. He has authored several specialized studies and contributed to research and institutional development projects.

Cătălin Ioan Clipa - is an Associate Professor, specializing in Organizational Behavior and Human Resource Management. His research focuses on Strategic HRM and the interaction between national culture and organizations. He has five years of experience as an HR manager.

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Alexandra Luciana Guță - is an Associate Professor teaching various Management-related subjects, including Organizational Knowledge Management and the Alignment of HR Strategy with Organizational Strategy.

Carmen Claudia Aruștei - is a Lecturer, PhD in Management, with teaching and research interests in Human Resource Management—particularly in employee motivation—Management, and Diversity Management. She is involved in student mobility projects.

Elena-Sabina Turnea - is a Lecturer and Postdoctoral Researcher in Management. She has won multiple awards for outstanding achievements in scientific research. She has authored/co-authored over 40 scientific publications and teaches Management and Human Resource Management in several European projects.

References

- [1]. Panaite, Nica; Andrei Stefan Neșțian (Coord.). 2024. *Managementul organizatiei. Concepte si practici [Organizational management. Concepts and practices]*. Iași: Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Publishing, ISBN: 978-606-714-842-8,
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